

REFLECTION OF NATIONAL CULTURE IN UZBEK-ENGLISH WEDDING CEREMONIES

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Abstract. *In this scientific work, we will focus on the national-cultural traditions of the wedding ceremonies of the Uzbek people.*

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Marriage is a reflection of family relations, recognized as the main link of society. Its main purpose is to make the first step of a young man and a girl on the threshold of a new life together towards a happy life known to the people, distant relatives and neighbors, and to reveal to the public the agreement of two young people to marry each other.

In addition to the fact that the wedding ceremony is celebrated in different ways in the nations of the world, it is distinguished by its own terms and procedure. In this regard, scientists such as D.D.Manukyan, Y.A.Sorokin, d.A.Gilfanova conducted research on the wedding ceremony.

It should be said that English and Uzbek wedding ceremonies are unique, with more differences than similarities. The traditions, customs and traditions of these two peoples are inextricably linked with their culture, way of life and traditions belonging to their own nation. Therefore, the etymology, that is, the history of the origin of many genres of wedding ceremonies, some of them have a religious character.

The traditions of the wedding ceremony begin with the choice of the bride and going to her house for marriage. In the Uzbek nation, when choosing a bride, her behavior, age, appearance, and close relatives are considered important. These processes are carried out through the rituals of "seeing a girl", "seeing a house". After the bride is chosen, the ceremony of "breaking bread" and "giving bread" is held, in which one of the elderly, respected women breaks bread as a sign of unity and agreement between the two families. (Fatiha is the betrothal ceremony of a girl and a boy before the wedding).

For example, the first ritual that initiates "Nikoh" wedding ceremonies is matchmaking, and the first examples of matchmakers can be found in the Orhun-Enasoy inscriptions of the VII-VIII centuries. In the epigraph of the great statesman Tonyuquq (7th century), the word "sov" was used in the sense of speech. "Sab" means "word" and "sabchi" means "messenger". "- he writes. So, the initial concepts and views about the family, courtship have come down to us from ancient times.

As for the wedding ceremonies of the English peoples, the wedding ceremony in them is completely different from the Uzbek weddings, for example, in them, complex customs and rituals are performed by the wedding participants, relying on a number of ancient beliefs: fetishism, totemism, worshipping the spirits of ancestors, fire and other there are customs of performing a number of demonological manifestations.

There are many examples of this. In particular, in the English nation, there are many cases of young people who are in love with each other running away from their parents to start a family

and marrying secretly. In this way, they promote the belief that young people are allowed freedom in choosing a spouse.

Uzbek wedding ceremonies are widely studied and are being studied by many people as one of our priceless values that reflect the culture, history, characteristics and stages of development of our nation. The history of Uzbek weddings, their stage of development, genre characteristics have been widely studied by a number of scholars. In this field, A. Ashirov ("Ancient beliefs and ceremonies of the Uzbek people"), K. Kubakov ("Wedding and wedding ceremonies in the past and present"), H. Muin ("About the wedding and mourning ceremony"), H. Sulaymonova ("In Uzbekistan history and present of wedding traditions"), H. Umurova ("On the terms of the wedding ceremony in English and Uzbek languages"), Z. Alimova ("Comparative analysis of lexemes related to the wedding ceremony in English and Uzbek peoples"), H. Ismailov ("Uzbek weddings"), M. Askarov ("Wedding: yesterday, today, tomorrow-ethnographic analysis") and others conducted scientific research.

In the marriage system of the Uzbek people: betrothal, betrothal, house visit, meeting, blessing wedding, wedding send-off (mazar), girl's wedding (girls' meeting), marriage education, bride's wedding, bride's greeting, charlari, god's call (father saw, girl saw) there are rituals and ancient traditions related to them. Most of them are still preserved and celebrated. Among them, marriage, cradle and circumcision are among the oldest rituals.

According to the civil law passed in England in 1653, a civil marriage ceremony by a justice of the peace is prescribed for a formal marriage, in which the priest of the church must present a certificate called for a public wedding. If one of the newlyweds is under 21 years of age, their parents' permission is required. Also, in some regions of England, it is forbidden to exchange rings during the wedding ceremony.

Since 1753, only marriages concluded in specially registered Anglican churches have been recognized as legal. Before 1990, it was possible to get married only in the church where one of the bride or groom will live in the future. That is, secretly marrying in foreign territory is prohibited by law.

The old English wedding tradition has long been held before Christmas, and the reason for this is that there is plenty of food until the New Year. For example, in England it is even customary to get married in September - based on the belief that couples who get married in September will be rich for life and live well together. The bride was given a decorative horseshoe on her wrist - it was believed to bring her good luck. When the bride entered the church, they sprinkled her with wheat. Nowadays, it is customary to sprinkle wheat not only on the bride, but also on the groom, and not on the entrance hall, but on the exit hall after the wedding. In some places, besides wheat, colored rice, candy, rose petals, etc. are sprinkled on the bride and groom.

The same aspect is also found in Uzbek wedding ceremonies. For example, at Uzbek weddings, there is a tradition of throwing sugar and sugar to the bride and groom at the gate of the house, so that they may have a sweet life. (this custom is also performed when the baby comes home and when the child takes its first steps). And the children pick it up. And in English wedding ceremonies, young children hardly participate.

It should be said that in all historical stages of Uzbek weddings, its main basis is religious marriage education. Wedding ceremonies, which have become an eternal value and have been inherited by us from the past, have been mixed with Udum and rituals before Islam and after Islam. In particular, to protect young people from the evil eye and calamities, they circle around the

bonfire, put a big cover over their heads, sprinkle sweets and coins to wish them a happy life, make them sit on their laps, wish them to be rich, and treat them with boiled eggs. special events were held. «Ko'rapa qavish», «Maslahat oshi», «Sabzi to'g'rar», «Mol yoyar» and other parts have reached today without any changes. Even now, these ceremonies are held in the circle of relatives and neighbors, just like before. In addition, there are no additional news to these events. I mean, today's weddings are held with equal participation of women and men, and it is customary to bring famous artists to the wedding.

Until the 20th century, weddings were held in homes, but by the 70s of the 20th century, the tradition of holding wedding ceremonies in restaurants and cafes began. Most notably, the bride and groom's dresses, which are the reason for the wedding, have also changed. The burqas and thick headscarves of the brides were replaced by a fata dress made according to modern fashion. Only the national cloak and turban worn by the groom remained. In addition, the number of wedding ceremony participants has increased relatively.

Also, in the 70s and 80s, the bride and groom and their "accompanying" friends went to the monuments of the city together, laid flowers, took pictures, videotaped, and put rings on each other. At the same time, especially in the capital, the composition of the bride's sarpo became more "expensive" with items ranging from tableware, furniture sets to refrigerators, in addition to traditional items. At the end of the 20th century, due to the sharp increase in spending on wedding ceremonies, even in Tashkent, challari and wedding receptions began to be held together.

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